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Data Review

Data Citation

Anhelina Hrytsei (2025): The Economist's Ukraine War-Fire Model (published on The Economist), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/F0C40123-0756-4622-A5CE-E1528A0FCBBF>

Abstract

The model detects war-related fires in Ukraine during the ongoing armed conflict with Russia to approximate patterns of military activity. It combines satellite imagery from NASA's Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) with synthetic-aperture radar (SAR) data. FIRMS, originally developed to monitor forest fires, uses infrared sensors and provides information about fires from multiple satellites that pass over each location at least twice per day. Because it is sensitive to cloud cover, it often fails to record fires when skies are overcast, especially in winter. SAR, which works by sending out pulses of energy and recording the reflections, captures changes in the shape of objects and is unaffected by weather conditions, although it may miss activity in sparsely populated areas.

To distinguish war-related fires from other types, The Economist developed a machine-learning algorithm built on 100 separate models trained to predict fire activity in non-war years. When at least 95 of these models confirm that fire activity in a specific location and time is abnormally high compared with pre-war numbers, the incident is coded as war-related.

The model has several limitations. First, satellites detect fires by sensing the heat they produce, but this process may be obstructed by weather conditions (such as cloud cover) or if the fires have stopped and the area cooled down before a satellite passed overhead. Second, the statistical method used by The Economist to detect war-related fires is probabilistic and relies on strict thresholds, which can result in real war-related incidents being excluded because they do not meet the criteria of abnormality. Finally, the model generally cannot distinguish war-related fires from non-war-related ones during periods of extremely high temperatures.

The model's results are published and regularly updated in The Economist, while the source code and underlying data are available on The Economist's GitHub page, which also hosts plots and interactive visualizations. The folder "output-data" contains downloadable .csv files on territorial control (based on the Institute for the Study of War data), cloud cover across Ukraine, dates of successfully acquired fire data, FIRMS updates,

fires by oblast, strikes by location and day, war-related fires, and several other indicators.

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Abstract

The Economist's Ukraine War-Fire Model is a tracking system that uses satellite imagery of fires in Ukraine, analyzed with a machine-learning algorithm, to determine whether they are war-related. The model aims to provide an objective and reliable approximation of patterns of military activity and changes in territorial control by comparing pre-war fire data from a given area with data collected during the war. Excess fires are coded as war-related.

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Data Review: The Economist's Ukraine War-Fire Model

The Ukraine War-Fire Model, developed by The Economist, is a tracking system that uses satellite imagery of fires in Ukraine, analyzed with a machine-learning algorithm, to determine whether they are war-related. The satellite imagery comes from NASA's Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) and synthetic-aperture radar (SAR) remote-sensing technology. The machine-learning algorithm consists of 100 separate models that estimate baseline fire data from the pre-war years and compare it with data collected during the full-scale war. Excess fires are coded as war-related. The model's goal is to provide an objective and reliable approximation of patterns of military activity and changes in territorial control, which cannot be achieved or definitively verified using more conventional approaches, such as open-source intelligence, because of limited information and restricted access to specific areas. The data is updated every couple of weeks on The Economist's dedicated page and on GitHub.

Methodological Foundation

The satellite imagery comes from NASA's Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) and synthetic-aperture radar (SAR) remote-sensing technology. FIRMS, originally developed to monitor forest fires, uses infrared sensors and provides data from multiple satellites that pass over each location at least twice per day. SAR, which works by sending out pulses of energy and recording the reflections, captures changes in the shape of objects. If an object is damaged or destroyed, the returning signal's strength will reflect this, and the data can be compared with the pre-war average.

The machine-learning algorithm analyzes the location of each fire in Ukraine and determines whether it is war-related "based on factors like historical fire counts and cloud cover."¹ If at least 95 out of 100 models agree that the number of fires is abnormal for a given location, the excess is coded as war-related. Excess fire activity in a given 0.1° latitude by 0.1° longitude cell of Ukraine on a particular day is defined as being so large that it has less than a 5% probability of occurring in a normal year. To be coded as war-related, incidents have to meet these criteria:

- Occur twice within a single cell located less than 50 km away.
- Be separated by at least 7 days but no more than 180 days (i.e., two spaced-out events within a six-month period).
- An additional fire event is also coded as war-related if it occurs in the same cell less than 10 days after the above conditions have been met (assuming

¹ The Economist, "Data from Satellites Reveal the Vast Extent of Fighting in Ukraine," The Economist, February 23, 2023, <https://www.economist.com/interactive/briefing/2023/02/23/data-from-satellites-reveal-the-vast-extent-of-fighting-in-ukraine>.

that agricultural or other routine fire activity typically does not resume until at least 10 days after an area has experienced a war-related event).²

To further assess the model's reliability, the locations of incidents coded as war-related are compared with openly available data on frontline developments, primarily the Institute for the Study of War's (ISW) reports. Explanatory factors (like the appearance of new weapons or political developments) are also considered by the authors when interpreting the data.³

Limitations

The model has several limitations, acknowledged by the authors. First, satellites detect fires by sensing the heat they produce, but this process may be obstructed by weather conditions or if the fires have stopped and the area cooled down before a satellite passed overhead. FIRMS is sensitive to cloud cover, which is why it often fails to record fires when skies are overcast, especially in winter. SAR, on the other hand, is unaffected by weather conditions. However, it may miss activity in sparsely populated areas which produce weaker and more diffuse radar reflections.⁴

Second, the statistical method used by The Economist to detect war-related fires is probabilistic and relies on strict thresholds, which can result in real war-related incidents being excluded because they do not meet the defined criteria of abnormality.⁵

Third, the model generally cannot distinguish war-related fires from non-war-related ones during periods of extremely high temperatures, as occurred from April 4 to April 11, 2023, when no incidents were coded as war-related.⁶

Finally, the detected fire locations are not fully precise and may deviate by up to 1 km, depending on the satellite.⁷

Usage

The data is publicly available on GitHub and includes output files in .csv and .RDS formats, in particular:

² Andreas Moor and Sondre Ulvund Solstad, "The Economist War-Fire Model," GitHub, April 2, 2024, <https://github.com/TheEconomist/the-economist-war-fire-model>.

³ The Economist, "Mapping the Ukraine War: Where Is the Latest Fighting?," The Economist, n.d., <https://www.economist.com/interactive/graphic-detail/ukraine-fires>.

⁴ The Economist, "Data from Satellites Reveal the Vast Extent of Fighting in Ukraine," The Economist, February 23, 2023, <https://www.economist.com/interactive/briefing/2023/02/23/data-from-satellites-reveal-the-vast-extent-of-fighting-in-ukraine>.

⁵ Andreas Moor and Sondre Ulvund Solstad, "The Economist War-Fire Model," GitHub, April 2, 2024, <https://github.com/TheEconomist/the-economist-war-fire-model>.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ The Economist, "Mapping the Ukraine War: Where Is the Latest Fighting?," The Economist, n.d., <https://www.economist.com/interactive/graphic-detail/ukraine-fires>.

- Areas of control daily summary (areas_of_control_daily_summary.csv);
- Cloud cover in Ukraine by day (cloud_cover_in_ukraine_by_day.csv);
- Cloud cover in Ukraine by day with forecast for recent days (cloud_cover_in_ukraine_by_day_with_forecast_for_recent_day.csv);
- Fires based on territorial control status (control_status_of_fires_II.csv);
- Dates of successfully acquired fire data (dates_of_successfully_acquired_fire_data.csv);
- FIRMS updates for Ukraine (dates_of_successfully_acquired_fire_data_RU.csv);
- FIRMS updates for Russia (firms_update.csv);
- Fire activity by day by oblasts in Ukraine and Russia (oblast_activity_by_day.csv);
- Strikes by location and day (strikes_by_location_and_day.csv);
- Fires in Ukraine (ukraine_fires.csv);
- War-related fires in Ukraine (ukraine_war_fires.csv);
- War-related fires by ADM3 (war_fires_by_ADM3.csv).⁸

Table 1. Variables in the files output-data/ukraine_fires.csv and output-data/ukraine_war_fires.csv (September 2025).⁹

Variable Name	Description
LATITUDE	Latitude of fire event in decimal degrees
LONGITUDE	Longitude of fire event in decimal degrees
date	Date of fire event in "year-month-day" format (e.g. 2023-09-15)
ACQ_TIME	Time of data acquisition by satellite in 24-hour format (e.g. 22:50)
id_w_time	ID of cell fire is detected in (given by longitude, latitude, day of year, and year, separated by underscores)
id	ID of cell fire is detected in (given by longitude, latitude, separated by underscore)
x	Longitude of cell fire is detected in (decimal degrees — midpoint)
y	Latitude of cell fire is detected in (decimal degrees — midpoint)

⁸ Andreas Moor and Sondre Ulvund Solstad, "The Economist War-Fire Model," GitHub, April 2, 2024, <https://github.com/TheEconomist/the-economist-war-fire-model>.

⁹ Ibid.

year	Year (e.g. 2005)
time_of_year	Day of the year (e.g. January 3 = 3)
fire	Whether fire was detected at this location at this time (TRUE, FALSE)
pop_density	Average population density of cell fire was detected in
city	Settlement the fire was detected in
in_urban_area	TRUE if fire was detected as being within an urban area, otherwise FALSE
pop_exact	Population density at fire location
excess_fire	Number of fires in cell beyond prediction for a particular cell and date, assuming no cloud cover
predicted_fire	Number of fires in cell predicted for a particular cell and date, assuming no cloud cover
fire_in_window	Observed fires for a particular cell and date
war_fire	Whether a specific fire is assessed as war-related by the model
sustained_excess	Whether a cell has seen sustained excess fire activity
id_big	Location rounded to nearest degree longitude and latitude, given as rounded longitude and latitude separated by an underscore
length_of_war_fire_area	Number of separate days with fires assessed as war-related in area, defined by rounding locations to nearest degree longitude and latitude
war_fire_restrictive	Whether this specific fire was assessed as abnormal
in_ukraine_held_area	Whether fire took place in an area assessed as Ukraine-controlled by the ISW (not within areas assessed as controlled by Russia by the ISW)
fires_per_day	Number of fires in Ukraine on a given date
war_fires_per_day	Number of fires classified as war-related in Ukraine on given date

fires_per_day_in_ukraine_held_area	Number of fires in Ukraine on date in areas assessed as Ukraine-controlled by the ISW
war_fires_per_day_in_ukraine_held_area	Number of fires classified as war-related in Ukraine on a given date
fires_per_day_in_russia_held_area	Number of fires in Ukraine on a given date in areas not assessed as Ukraine-controlled by the ISW
war_fires_per_day_in_russia_held_area	Number of fires classified as war-related in Ukraine on a given date in areas not assessed as Ukraine-controlled by the ISW

There is also a collection of downloadable scripts in .R and .sh.¹⁰

In terms of geographical coverage, the data concerns only Ukraine and parts of Russia. Other countries or armed conflicts are not included, which limits the comparability and cross-application of the data. The general approach to approximating patterns of military activity and changes in territorial control is well-documented and could potentially be replicated in the analysis of other armed conflicts. The data may also be used to cross-verify specific strike locations reported by official sources or the media.

Funding

Funding information for the project is unavailable. The Economist is operated by The Economist Group, “a global media and information-services company” whose revenue comes primarily from subscriptions.¹¹

Note

This data review was produced by Anhelina Hrytsei as part of an Erasmus Traineeship at the Research Center for East European Studies at the University of Bremen.

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ “The Economist Group: Results,” The Economist Group, March 31, 2025, <https://www.economistgroup.com/results>.